

INTERETHNIC HARMONY-HIGH VALUE

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Abstract. The concept of interethnic harmony represents the fostering of positive relationships, understanding, and collaboration among individuals from diverse ethnic backgrounds. In a world marked by cultural diversity, achieving interethnic harmony is of high value as it contributes to social cohesion, peace, and sustainable development. This abstract explores the importance of interethnic harmony, emphasizing its role in promoting tolerance, respect, and mutual appreciation among different ethnic groups. The abstract delves into the key factors influencing interethnic harmony, including education, cultural exchange programs, and effective communication strategies. It highlights the significance of embracing cultural diversity as a source of strength rather than division, emphasizing the shared human experience that unites people across ethnic boundaries. Furthermore, the abstract addresses the role of government policies, institutions, and grassroots initiatives in nurturing interethnic harmony. It discusses the positive impact of inclusive policies that promote equal opportunities, social justice, and the protection of minority rights. The abstract also recognizes the challenges associated with achieving interethnic harmony, such as stereotypes, prejudice, and historical tensions. It emphasizes the need for education and awareness campaigns to challenge these negative perceptions and foster a more inclusive and harmonious society.

Keywords: Interethnic Harmony, Ethnic Diversity, Social Cohesion, Tolerance, Cultural Exchange, Respect, Mutual Appreciation, Inclusive Policies, Social Justice, Minority Rights, Cultural Diversity, Effective Communication, Education

Interethnic relations can be viewed as a unique, complex and flashy system. This specificity makes it necessary, firstly, to realize the political, socio-economic, cultural needs and interests of Ethnos, which are considered a component of the national structure of society, and secondly, to correctly assess the processes taking place in interethnic relations and to solve existing problems, as well as to develop measures of a complex nature, to solve And their successful solution allows you to organize the foresight and control of the character and direction of changes in national life and direct the spiritual and educational, economic and organizational and technical potential of state authorities, political parties, movements and public organizations to solve existing problems. With the attention of the essence, what goals are solved by the mentioned tasks, it serves

as the basis for the formation of a certain type of interethnic relationship with positive or negative content, which practically does not leave room for stichiality. In particular, national inequality, an inexhaustible view of other nations, and in certain cases the primacy of antagonism, is indicative of the negative content of interethnic relations.

When applied to our country, it should be noted that ethnic relations are characterized by having a positive content that can be described as interethnic harmony.

First President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan I.A.Karimov addressed to the participants of the solemn meeting on the 10th anniversary of the establishment of the Republican center of international culture the nature of the interethnic relations decided in our country, noting "with special pride and pride, I would like to say that Uzbekistan has a lot of wealth, but our greatest wealth, our highest value, this is peace, interethnic friendship and

Such a conclusion is also confirmed by the results of sociological studies. In a survey conducted by the Republican Center for the study of public opinion on the topic "multinational Uzbekistan" and attended by people of different nationalities, 80.6% supported the idea that the greatest achievement of independent Uzbekistan is peace and stability, interethnic and interethnic harmony in our common home. The fact that the absolute majority (96.4 percent) positively assessed existing interethnic relations can also be evidence of our opinion. These positive assessments are primarily the result of the creation of appropriate conditions for representatives of different nationalities and nationalities to actively participate in all spheres of social life.

The positive changes that took place in the field of population consciousness, psyche and interethnic relations during the years of independence can also be seen in the stabilization of the processes of mythation. This can be explained by a number of factors. First of all, it should be shown that in our republic it is seen as a factor that has the power of creation, and not as a destructive force to multinationalism. In particular, the search for "culprits" for the losses of the period of occupation, unlike some former Soviet republics, became of fundamental importance. It was extremely important in a situation where it was strong to look at the state as a guarantee of security. Secondly, in the early years of independence, there was a lack of confidence in tomorrow, or rather, the inability to clearly imagine it. This annoyance has been brought to an end by the national policies that are being pursued to this day.

In the domination of interethnic harmony in our country, the relationship between the Tajik, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Turkmen peoples, whose total content of the Republic's population is about 10 percent, has been in partnership and cooperation with Uzbek and Karakalpaks for centuries, is important. The peoples of Central Asia – Tajik, Turkmen, Kyrgyz, Kazakhs and Uzbeks – do not have much to say about our historical unity, Cultural Unity, religious unity, in a word, our truly human unity. The long-standing unity and striving for each other of our peoples is clearly felt in every home, in every family, in every village and in every city.

In the further deepening of the cultural and educational foundations of the friendship of the peoples of Central Asia, it is necessary to emphasize the huge organizing and unifying role of the idea of "Turkestan-our common home". After all, this idea provides an opportunity, first of all, to preserve and develop unity, which arose as a result of the territorial, social, ethnocultural and religious closeness of the peoples of the region. Secondly, the needs and interests of one people do not allow such aspirations of other peoples to come true at the expense of discrimination or non-recognition. Thirdly, the path of constructive cooperation will lay the groundwork for the eventual resolution of possible conflicts. Fourth, the interaction and enrichment of the cultures of peoples with one Root opens the way for the Gobi-historical process. And, nyahoyat, fifth, to instill the view that there is a desire for national superiority, including various fictions of the following country peoples. Juxtaposition strikes at attempts to create conflict. After all, for us, Turon is a symbol of the cultural rather than super-political unity of the Turkic-speaking peoples of the region. In addition, our common cultural, historical and anthropological roots also connect us with the Tajik people. This circumstance gives us the full right to consider our culture as a synthesis of Turkish and Persian cultures that are to some extent unique to Central Asia. So, "Turkestan", as it is interpreted in some cases, refers not only to Turkic peoples, but also to the entire population of the territory, which also indicates the enormous importance of the idea of "Turkestan – our common home" for the peoples of the region.

In place of the conclusion, it can be noted that multiculturalism is also characteristic of Uzbekistan. In our Republic, along with the main Nation – Uzbeks, more than a hundred nationalities with their own culture and traditions live. Their share of the total composition of the country's population exceeds 20 percent. Such multi-nationalism is the result of protracted socio-historical processes. According to reports, in 1897, representatives of 70 nationalities and

nationalities lived in the current territory of our country, in 1926 the number reached 91, in 1959-113, in 1979-123, in 1989-136. The presence of representatives of different nationalities gives a unique colorfulness to the life of our country.

Society is the result of the interaction of different processes, the unity of different social layers. It is the main criterion that determines the qualitative state of society for interethnic relations in the context of polyethnicity, and allows interethnic solidarity to be viewed as an important factor in peace and stability in the social space where people of different nationalities live together.

In conclusion, the abstract underscores that interethnic harmony is not only a moral imperative but also an essential element for building resilient, vibrant, and sustainable communities. It encourages further research and practical interventions aimed at promoting understanding, empathy, and collaboration among people of diverse ethnic backgrounds. Ultimately, the pursuit of interethnic harmony contributes to the creation of a more just, peaceful, and interconnected global society.